

Influence of Appraisal System Criteria on Employees' Motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya

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Abstract:- Public service employees' motivation has emerged as a complex issue globally, regionally as well as in Kenya. A systematic review of staffs' motivation is revealed by factors such as financial rewards, career development, continuous education resource availability and recognition. The County Government of Kisumu's department of roads, transport and public work honored its employee through recognition awards for the 99% of roads done, 2020-2021. The individual employees were awarded for showing dedication, responsibility and results. The other departments within the Kisumu county government (governance, finance education, health and county assembly) have never had such recognition, a show of selective implementation of performance reward system by county departments. The general objective was to study the effects of performance appraisal on employees' motivation at county government of Kisumu, Kenya. Specifically the study sought to; determine the effect of appraisal system criteria on employees' motivation at county government of Kisumu. The study was anchored on goal setting theory and expectancy theory. The researcher adopted a correlational research design to study the relationship between the variables. The target population of study consisted of 876 employees of county government of Kisumu drawn from the 8 departments and consisting of supervisors and junior staffs. Stratified random sampling was used to draw a sample of 375 respondents from the population. Primary data was obtained using structured questionnaire. A pilot study was conducted in Vihiga County. A Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.813 was obtained thus implying the study instrument was reliable. Validity was ascertained through expert review at the department of Business Administration at Maseno University. The primary data collected was analyzed using regression analysis. The findings shows that appraisal system criteria has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation ($\beta=.309$, $p<.05$) and accounts for 36.6% variance in employee motivation. This implies that performance appraisal, entailing appraisal system criteria positively enhanced employee motivation and consequently their work. It was concluded that appraisal criteria has a positive influence on employee motivation, and recommended that the county improves its appraisal criteria. This means that all the constructs defining performance appraisal had a positive and significant effect on employee motivation. The research is significant to academicians the field of

research, practitioners in human resource field as well as institutions

Keywords:- Appraisal, System, Criteria, Employee Motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Performance appraisal is a process that evaluate the output of individual employee and the measure to improve it so that it can contribute to overall organization performance (Singh et al, 2018). Consistently, to reap much from the employees they must be motivated. Employee performance appraisal emphasizes the job development and growth plans for the employees (Malongwe, 2015). Its significance is attested where employees resolve to maintain accurate objective records of employee performance in order to defend themselves against possible changes of dissemination in connection with human resource action like discharge, promotions and salary increment. Jalal and Putri (2015) places emphasis on the people if an organization needs to have sustainable competitive advantage. Effective performance involve effectiveness and efficiency of employees in how they execute their assigned jobs within the framework of the laid standards (Ibeogu & Ozturen, 2015). A good performance approach should be able to relate to the strategic goals of the organization, focus on organizational output as well as providing a basis for the feedback for improvement.

Employee motivation refers to employees' goals, techniques used to achieve their goals and their personal conduct that influences their behaviour to accomplish those goals and aspects influencing employees of an organization to conduct themselves in a particular manner (Maimunah, 2020). Consistently, motivation is a product of a set of internal and external factors that influence an employee to choose the best course of action and maintain good behaviour which propel the laid goals. Moreover, employees are motivated when they anticipate that their inputs make them achieve their goals and thereafter being rewarded for the same efforts (Munene, 2013). According to Idowu (2017), motivation is the willingness to expand energy to achieve a goal or reward. It is the primary energizer that drives employees' effort towards predetermined goals of an organization. Essentially, the output of every company depends on how well the output of employees is evaluated and appraised. Employee motivation is concerned with

boosting their morale so as to achieve the mission and vision of the organization. Employers have accepted the reality that motivation increases productivity of the work force. It stimulates the employees' thirst to work with minimal supervision and internal pressure. It is significant in implementing employee performance –achieving goals and cementing cohesion in a team based environment. This is done by ensuring employees' workplace goals and values are aligned with the organization's mission and vision resulting into high performance and increased productivity (Jalal & Putri, 2015).

There are two different kinds of motivation: extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation refers to an individual's personal interest, satisfaction and enjoyment. It is affected by internal factors such as passion for work, love for challenges and anxiety. Employees may not be able to identify the reasons for their intrinsic motivation (Faizal et al., 2021). Extrinsic Motivation is external; According to Singh et al., (2018), it comes as a result of pressure or forces outside an employee. An employee who is extrinsically motivated works because he/she is afraid of punishment or losing reward attached to high performance. They usually work hard since they want to be rewarded by their employers. Organizations tend to motivate their employees extrinsically by promising rewards. These rewards provide satisfaction and pleasure that the employee may not necessarily enjoy an activity to perform well in order to receive some kind of reward or to avoid negative consequences (Caesar, 2018). Intrinsic motivation is better than extrinsic motivation because, with intrinsic motivation, one is driven to search for knowledge so as to increase one's skill needed for a job. However, both forms of motivation are necessary where maximum and long term results is to be achieved. The most important thing is to have a balance between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation as proposed in the study.

The Constitution of Kenya 2010 allowed the country to transition from a centralized system to a decentralized system in 2013 with key functional areas being devolved. The decentralized system created the 47 county governments. The national government retained the three arms: the National Executive, the Legislature and the Judiciary. The judiciary was not devolved into counties and therefore county governments comprised the Executive and The Legislature. To ensure accountability of civil servants involved in provision of public services in the county, the county performance management system and capacity building framework was developed in 2016 (CIMES, 2019). Most counties have initiated the process of performance appraisal such as capacity building, vetting and signing of performance contracts, identification of indicators and targets. However they have not consistently undertaken the rest of the process i.e. mid-year performance review, evaluation and release of evaluation results. Some counties have not implemented performance appraisal fully (CEG, 2018). County government of Kisumu is one of the former administrative districts of the former Nyanza province in Western Kenya. Its head quarter is Kisumu City. The first governor for the county was Jackton Ranguma who assumed

office in 2013 at the advent of devolution while the current governor is Prof. Peter Anyang Nyong'o. The metropolitan county employ many people from different ethnic communities. However, there are reports of limited employment opportunities for its population. Many industries in the county collapsed like Miwani Sugar Company, Chemelil Sugar Company and Kisumu Cotton Mills. The county's remedial measures includes creating employment, improving labour force distribution, increasing human capital development and employee motivation. This is to create a triple effect in service delivery to the populace and revenue generation. To achieve all this the county leadership need to emphasize on the facets of performance appraisal which will motivate the employees into productivity like capacity building, choosing the best appraisal system criteria and providing performance appraisal feedback to the employees (KPMG, 2017). Performance appraisal yields techniques used by employees to contribute to the achievement of the county goal objectives as spelt out in County Integrated Development Plan 2018 for better resource utilization. It propels communication between employees from different departments and their supervisors who provide them with feedback on performance. The successful implementation of performance appraisal process leads to development of employee potential, their motivation and improved productivity. However, this has not been fully implemented by all departments in county government of Kisumu.

Globally, many studies which examined the effects of performance appraisal on employee motivation reveal mixed results, they reported weak, positive and negative results. Lamphon (2018) studied the impact of performance appraisal on private sector employee motivation in Saudi Arabia using population of 100 employees. It was concluded that performance appraisal is related to employee motivation and it is a very important aspect of achieving organization goals and to improving the organizational performance. Maimunah (2020) analyzed the influence of performance appraisal towards employees' motivation and productivity in Tribunnews.com-solo, Indonesia. A population of 50 employees was considered. They were classified in terms age, gender, education and work experience. The result showed that performance appraisal had a significant influence on employees' motivation and productivity. Lira et al., (2016) studied performance appraisal as a motivational tool in the Public administration. SPSS was used in data analysis and from the findings it was revealed that Integrated System of Performance Management and Appraisal in the Public Sector (SIADAP) has a negative contribution to the functioning of the Portuguese public administration. Iqbal et al (2016) studied the impact of performance appraisal on employees' performance involving the moderating role of motivation in banking industry of Dera Ghazi Khan. It was revealed that a positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Motivation as the moderator positively affected the relationship between performance appraisal and employee performance. Saeed (2016) studied the impact of performance appraisal and motivation on employees output in banking sector of Sahiwal, Pakistan. It was concluded that

there is a positive relationship between work performance, motivation and performance appraisal.

Despite the attempts to study performance appraisal and employee motivation, no study has focused on investigating employee motivation using improvement of salaries, provision of awards and promotions and improved working condition. Lamphon (2018) used 150 employees in his study while Maimunah (2020) used 50 employees in the study. However, the latter adopted exploratory and causal research design while the former employed a descriptive research design. Lira et al., (2016) on the contrary used 334 employees of public administration, Iqbal et al (2016) incorporated 150 employees in his study while Saeed (2016) used a population of 200 employees of banks with a quantitative approach.

➤ *Statement of the problem*

The county governments in Kenya have shown weak operation performance according to the Auditor General’s report of 2019 where employees felt less motivated with the results of appraisal process and general administration. Particularly, in county government of Kisumu, industrial action like strikes and go-slow and many staff complains have been witnessed which resulted into poor service delivery by the employees. The poor services includes garbage collection, solid waste management and poor roads. Poor service delivery is equivalent to poor performance and low employee productivity. The pointer to this were lack of staff motivation, subjective performance appraisal, leadership methods and employee management methods. The report by the Office of Controller of Budget have shown Kisumu county own revenue collection for the first half of the year FY 2013/2014 to FY 2019/2020 have shown dwindling performance. The first half of FY 2019/2020, the county generated a total of Kshs. 363.96Million own sourced revenue. This shown a decrease of 10.2% when compared to 405.3Million reported during the same period in FY 2018/2019 which represented 25.3% of the annual target. The salaries for county employees were delayed and

one of the contributing factor was revenue collections. The contracted health workers downed their tools after three months of probation where the county government failed their promise of deploying them to their work station after the said period. However, the county department of roads, transport and public work honored its staffs through recognition awards for the 99% of roads done in 2020-2021. The individual staffs were awarded for showing dedication, responsibility, respect and results. The other departments within the Kisumu county government (governance, finance education, health and county assembly) have never had such recognition, a show of selective implementation of performance reward system based on appraisal criteria by county departments. Gradual weakening of employee motivation negatively influence performance. Reviewed literature links performance appraisal and motivation. Many studies were done globally, regionally and locally majority using descriptive research methodology. Few studies reviewed investigated the relationship between performance appraisal and employees’ motivation in the county governments. There is little known about how appraisal system criteria, relate with employee motivation.

➤ *Purpose of the study*

The study sought to establish the influence of performance appraisal on employees’ motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya. Specifically, the study sought to establish the influence of appraisal system criteria on employees’ motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya.

➤ *Study Hypothesis*

- *H₀₁: Appraisal system criteria does not have a significant influence on employees’ motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya.*

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

➤ *Goal Setting Theory*

The theory by Locke (1968) postulates that employees who have clear intentions in a work environment are highly motivated. Specific goals accelerate work performance thus high goals register higher level of outcome when compared to non-specific goals. Specificity of goals trigger internal morale of employees thus motivating them to perform the assigned jobs. Goal setting can play a significant role in enhancing people’s motivation and performance. People who set specific, challenging goals and commit

to these goals are more likely to try their best and persist in achieving the goals, which can lead to better performance and success. According to Locke (1968) employees are really motivated by well-defined goals and proper feedback and are more likely to accomplish these goals when they are specific and measurable. They work effectively when they are exposed to challenging goals. They will be forced to work hard to accomplish the challenging goals and in the process they sharpen their skills, receive positive results and positive recognition. The end results being consistent employee engagement, production capacity and satisfaction.

The results from previous studies showed that goal setting has a positive influence on workers' performance. However, these studies lacked theoretical framework to explain why and how goal setting influences work performance (Latham & Locke, 2007). Latham and Locke (2007) posits that in the field of organization and human resource management, goal setting can have an impact on employees' behavior and performance at work. Setting specific and measurable goals is more effective than setting unclear goals. Consistently, the theory is one of the most influential framework in motivational psychology that positively influence employees' performance.

Employees are usually motivated to work when their supervisors share with them feedback from the appraisal process from their individual contribution pegged on their Key Performance Indices (KPI). The appraisal feedback from management and supervisors pinpoint the discrepancies in their output when compared to the assigned jobs. The theory postulates that an employee is committed to well spelt-goals and determined to work towards achieving the organizational goals. Management By Objective (MBO) is one of the examples where goal setting theory is applied. The employee appraisal system and Management By Objective is centralized on fulfilling the goals set and achieving the set targets. Locke (1990) pointed out that there are some significant factors that can impact an individual's performance: core goal properties (e.g., specificity, challenge), moderators (e.g. ability, feedback, goal commitment), and mediators (e.g., choice, effort). Latham (2003) pointed out in one study that individuals who have specific, challenging, but attainable goals have better performance than those who set vague goals or do not set goals. Meanwhile, individuals should possess ability and have commitment to the goal to have better performance.

Employees feel motivated when they are fully involved in performance appraisal process. Locke (1990) explains ability as whether people possess skill or knowledge to finish the task. Feedback is also needed for people to decide whether they should put forth more effort or change their strategy. Moreover, goal commitment refers to whether individuals have the determination to realize the goal. In addition to ability, feedback, and commitment, task complexity is also considered important; it indicates that people tend to have better performance when the tasks are more straightforward. In addition, situational resources, the related resources or materials provided for individuals to achieve their goal, are also essential. Finally, self-efficacy refers to whether people are confident in doing something and that it will affect their goals and performance (Locke & Latham, 1990).

Specific and challenging goals along with appropriate feedback has positive effect on job performance. Moreover, employees are motivated to perform a task when their individual contribution is recognized even where the goals are superior and thought to be unachievable. The goals which are challenging usually leads to rewards such as recognition, promotions and salary increment. Goal setting theory is underpinning this study because it emphasizes on

performance appraisal process that specify goals and align them with performance to motivate employees towards achieving the goals set by an organization promptly. Consequently, goal setting increases performance where they are specific and motivating and provides feedback on the work done. The goals are a pointer and barometer to how much work should be done with efforts commensurate assigned task (Locke & Latham, 2007).

➤ *Empirical Literature Review*

Faizal et al., (2021) examined the impact and analysis of performance appraisal on employees' motivation and its effects on employee retention in banking sector. The researcher adopted mono – method where the researcher collected only one type of information quality and quantity. It was integrated with deduction method. Descriptive research design and explanatory explanation on the variable formed the foundation of the study. Data collection tool was survey questionnaire. The study identified 80 respondents out of which 65 employees were contacted. Survey questionnaire were developed and distributed online and analyzed with SPSS software. The findings revealed that performance appraisal had an impact on employee motivation. Appraisal method impact on employee behavior and his performance if financial institutions appraise and provides an opportunity to employees to grow in their organization therefore employee retention ratio will be more and work efficiency would increase. However, the study looked at employee motivation measured by how well the organization could retain them but failed to take care of employees' personal motivation towards self fulfilment. Furthermore, there is contextual difference between the two studies with the former focusing on banking sector. The current study will therefore adopt a correlational research design in establishing the influence of performance appraisal on motivation of employees of Kisumu county government.

Raboca et al., (2017) studied performance appraisal in Romanian local public institutions, satisfaction of local civil servants regarding the performance appraisal system. The study was carried out through a sociological survey where a number of 300 employed civil servants in Romania. The survey used 233 respondents who fully filled in the questionnaires representing 65%. A ten point Likert scale was adopted. It was concluded that technical aspects, the level of satisfaction regarding the performance appraisal system is influenced by ethical and moral aspects (justice and fairness of the system). It was revealed that there is a significant but not strong relationship between the level of satisfaction and the level of motivation of civil servants. However, the study failed to take care of facet of motivation; improvement of salaries, provision of awards & promotions and satisfaction and passion for work but only emphasized on ethical and moral aspects (justice and fairness of the system) of performance appraisal.

Caesar (2018) studied the effects of performance appraisal on employee motivation in two publishing firms. The study adopted exploratory research design with qualitative approach. The researcher purposively sampled 8 employees from both companies. Data was collected

through a structured interview where the respondents were audio recorded during one on one conversation. It was concluded that performance appraisal have effect on the motivation of employees and productivity of the firms. It was revealed that perceived fairness and objectivity can affect the effectiveness of performance appraisal in motivating the employees. Non-monetary incentives often tend to boost the intrinsic motivation of the employee while monetary and career related incentives tend to boost their extrinsic motivation. Appreciation awards often leads to satisfaction of employee emotionally boosting their intrinsic motivation. However, little is known about effect of performance appraisal techniques at Kisumu County since the study concentrated on publishing firms.

Idowu (2017) examined the effectiveness of performance appraisal system and its effects on employee motivation. The study adopted mixed method and anchored on positivist research paradigm. The study surveys employees at Shrines communication and interviews the HR manager. Primary data was collected using interview and questionnaire. Quantitative data was analyzed statistically using excel and SPSS 20. The study findings showed the presence of significant positive outcomes when the organization uses performance appraisal as a motivational tool and using more than one appraisal technique helps yields greater satisfaction and consequently higher motivation level. However, the study was concentrated on human resource managers who are policy makers and implementers but did not looked at junior staffs who are being appraised and thus affected by the appraisal process. The present study will focus on junior employees of county government.

Ndirangu and Mbugua (2016) examined the effects of appraisal system on employees' performance in Athi Water Services Board in Kenya. A descriptive research design with survey method was applied in this research. The study applied both stratified sampling and simple random sampling to the select the respondents. The findings revealed that failure to involve employees in the appraisal system create dissatisfaction hence making the implementation ineffective. It was concluded that appraisal feedback and rewarding help improve performance of staffs. However, the study stressed on employee involvement in the appraisal process and did not look at whether the employees were well trained on the appraisal process, the criteria used in appraisal was fair and the relevance of appraisal feedback to employees.

Singh and Rana (2014) studied the impact of performance appraisal on the motivation of teachers of professional institutions in Dehradun city. The study employed ex-post facto survey design. A sample of 170 teachers were randomly selected from a list of 650 teachers located in 7 professional institute. A five point Likert scale questionnaire was used in data collection where 26 questions were structured. Internal reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha method and Guttman Split-half coefficient. A total of 190 questionnaires were distributed out of which 170 were recovered resulting into 89.473%.

Data was analyzed using percentages, frequencies and multiple analysis. The results showed that performance appraisal is positively and significantly correlated with the motivation of teachers. When employees are involved in goal setting, they are motivated and they try their best to achieve the standard set for them. Goal setting and performance feedback significantly predicated motivation. However, the study was done in a different country and there is little known about performance appraisal in county government of Kisumu.

Singh et al., (2018) examined the impact of performance appraisal on employee motivation. The population of the study were working on Crest Steel and Power Pvt Ltd. The sample size was 50 employees from the department heads and staffs from the survey done. Random sampling technique was used in selecting the population. Quantitative and qualitative techniques were employed through interviews and closed ended questionnaires. The reliability test was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha. It was concluded that managers and employees takes performance appraisal seriously since they consider it an important factor to get motivated and work efficiently. Employees of an organization needs appropriate performance appraisal system. Performance appraisal thus has dominant effect on employee motivation. However, the current study looked at managers and employees as both being assessed but failed to investigate the role of supervisor/managers in appraising employees.

Odayo et.al., (2020) sought to examine the relationship between employee involvement and employee performance of part time lecturers in public universities in Kenya. The study adopted descriptive survey research design to collect data from a sample of 60 part time lecturers from four public universities in the western region of Kenya. The study used structured questionnaires to gather information from the respondents. The sampling technique used was stratified sampling and simple random sampling. It was analyzed descriptively using percentages, mean and standard deviation and also inferentially using regression and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation test. Employee involvement was found to be strongly positively correlated to employee performance ($r=0.665$; $p<0.01$). Employee involvement accounted for 44.2 % of the total variance in employee performance of part time lecturers in public universities. Thus the study found that employee involvement had a great influence on employee performance. The study recommends that public universities should adopt employee involvement programs to drive performance, growth and competitiveness on the regional and also the global market. Divergently, the study did not looked examine whether part-time lecturers were motivated by the appraisal process and offered conducive working environment but only emphasized on the output of the lecturers.

The studies reviewed showed mixed results between different components of performance appraisal and motivation. Some of the studies showed a weak relationship while others had a strong relationship. Faizal et al., (2021)

found a strong positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee motivation. Similarly, Caesar (2018) found a strong positive relationship between non-monetary incentives and intrinsic motivation of the employee. Idowa (2017) findings showed the presence of a strong significant positive outcomes when the organization uses performance appraisal as a motivational tool and using more than one appraisal technique helps yields greater satisfaction and consequently higher motivation level. Consistently, Singh et al., (2018) studies established that performance appraisal has dominant effect on employee motivation. Singh & Rana (2014) showed that performance appraisal is positively and significantly correlated with the motivation of teachers. Moreover, Ndirangu & Mbugua (2016), findings revealed that failure to involve employees in the appraisal system create dissatisfaction hence making the implementation ineffective. Divergently, Raboca et al., (2017) found that there is a significant but not strong relationship between the performance appraisal and the level of motivation of civil servants. Odero and Makori (2018) study found that employee involvement at 44.2 % had a great influence on employee performance. Faizal et al., (2021) adopted mono – method where the researcher collected only one type of information quality and quantity with population of 65 employees. However, Raboca et al., (2017) carried the study through a sociological survey where a number of 233 employed civil servants in Romania. While Singh & Rana (2014) studied the impact of performance appraisal on the motivation of teachers of professional institutions in Dehradun city using ex-post facto survey design. However, not one of the studies reviewed used correlational research design to measure the relationship between performance appraisal and employees’ motivation in the county governments. There is little known about how appraisal system criteria, appraisal feedback and employee training relate with employee motivation. Majority of these studies were done in other countries far from county government and were done on already developed countries and in different sectors.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design, which was carried out at County government of Kisumu. The target population of the study were employees of county government of Kisumu. The targeted population are 876 employees as per County Report (2021). The study adopted

stratified random sampling technique where each unit of the population has equal chance of being selected from the population and its attributes taken care of (Kothari 2004). Purposive sampling technique was used to select the employees and supervisors who are all involved directly in performance appraisal process. Therefore a sample size of 375 respondents was arrived at using Yamane’s formula (cited in Njugi & Muna 2021) as follow: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$ Where n is the sample size, N is the population size and e is the margin of error. $n = \frac{876}{1+876(0.05)^2}$

Since the research involved primary data it was collected using structured questionnaires on a five point Likert scale. Cronbach alpha revealed a high instrument ($\alpha=.885$) reliability which shows that the overall instrument (Questionnaire) was reliable. Face validity of the instrument was ascertained through review by two human resource experts from the Department of Business Administration Maseno University and Professionals in the area of Human Capital. Descriptive analysis was used to establish the composite mean which was then used in the regression. Regression analysis was used to establish the effect of Appraisal System Criteria on employee motivation.

➤ *Model Specification*

The multiple regression analysis was adopted to test cross sectional data:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Y= Dependent Variable (Motivation), X_1 = Appraisal System Criteria (ASC), β_0 =Y intercept in the equation, β_1 = Size and direction of causal effect of X_1 , the independent variable (Appraisal system criteria) on Y, the dependent variable (Motivation), ϵ = Residual in the equation

➤ *Findings and Discussions*

A total of 375 questionnaires were administered to the respondents who entailed supervisors and junior staff. The findings are presented as shown in Table 4.1 below.

➤ *Demographic Information*

Demographic information of the study respondents entailed their departments and categories, years of working experience and highest level of education. These are presented as shown in Table 1 using frequency counts and percentages.

Table 1 Demographic Information of the Study Respondents

Departments	Supervisors	%	Junior Staff	%	Total	%
Governance & Admin	4	6.1	15	7.3	25	6.7
Finance & Planning	3	4.5	9	4.4	17	4.4
Energy	3	4.5	22	10.7	30	7.9
Education	4	6.1	15	7.3	25	6.7
Roads	5	7.6	25	12.1	38	10.1
Health	23	34.8	56	27.2	114	30.6
County Assembly	11	16.7	23	11.2	51	13.6
City Hall	13	19.7	41	19.9	74	19.8
Total	66	24.0	206	74.0	372	100.0
Years of working experience		Frequency			Percent	
1-2 years		41			11.0	

3-4 years	78	21.0
5-6 years	142	38.2
7-8 years	89	23.9
9 years and more	22	5.9
Total	372	100.0
What is your highest level of education?	Frequency	Percent
Certificate	20	5.5
Diploma	127	33.8
Degree	183	49.3
Masters	22	5.9
PHD	20	5.5
Total	372	100.0

Source (Field Survey Data, 2022)

A larger number of respondents, 206(74%) were junior staff while the least, 66(24%) were supervisors. Majority of the respondents, 19.8% were health workers followed by 19.8% who were city hall workers, 13.6% who were county assembly workers. The least percentage, 4.4% were finance and planning and 6.7% government and administration workers. From the findings, majority, 142(38.2%) of the respondents had experience of 5-6 years followed by 23.9% who had experience of 7-8 years and 21.0% who had experience of 3-4 years. Therefore majority of the respondents had experience ranging from 3-8 years, which is sufficient for their knowledge on the study subject. Finally, the findings shows that majority, 183(49.3%) of the respondents highest level of education was degree followed by diploma, 127(33.8%). The other categories were few.

Therefore the respondents have formal education and have the necessary knowledge to respond on the study subject.

➤ *Employee Motivation at County Government of Kisumu*

The study outcome was employee motivation at county government of Kisumu. This was measured using four subscales which were: guaranteed payments and improvements of salaries, provision of award and promotions and improved working conditions. Respondents were therefore asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed with statements on each of the three measures using a scale of 1-5 in the range of 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. The findings are presented as shown in Table 2 using frequency counts, percentages, means and standard deviation.

Table 2 Employee Motivation Rating

Guaranteed payments and improvement of salaries	1	2	3	4	5	M	STD
My salary and allowances are paid on time.	134(36)	174(46.8)	20(5.4)	30(8.1)	14(3.8)	1.9	.97
Salary I receive is linked to the work I do.	81(21.8)	184(49.5)	59(15.9)	32(8.6)	16(4.3)	2.2	.96
I receive additional payment when my performance exceeds my targets.	145(39)	94(25.3)	99(26.6)	16(4.3)	18(4.8)	2.0	1.05
The current employment benefits package is fair and equitable.	35(9.4)	120(32.3)	31(8.3)	129(34.7)	57(15.3)	3.1	1.28
Provision of award and promotion							
There are opportunities for attending seminars, workshop and tours sponsored by county government for good performance.	107(28.8)	142(38.2)	22(5.9)	85(22.8)	16(4.3)	2.3	1.20
You are provided with individual awards for better performance.	39(10.5)	157(42.2)	137(36.8)	20(5.4)	19(5.1)	2.5	0.89
Employees who perform well in their role are fairly promoted and rewarded.	59(15.9)	178(47.8)	101(27.2)	22(5.9)	12(3.2)	2.4	0.97
County government use reward-based performance system that is made known to all employees	99(26.6)	116(31.2)	127(34.1)	21(5.6)	9(2.4)	2.3	1.02
Improved working conditions							
County government provide suitable job match to employee to meet employee preference.	57(15.3)	145(39)	119(32)	41(11)	10(2.7)	2.5	1.00
I am allowed to review my career plan annually to meet short term and long term goals of the county government.	99(26.6)	181(48.7)	69(18.5)	11(3)	12(3.2)	2.1	.99
County government is informative to employee on current changes, trends and future expectation	131(35.2)	186(50)	18(4.8)	26(7)	11(3)	1.9	.97
County government value employee’s personal suggestions on what constitute a good working environment.	162(43.5)	79(21.2)	100(26.9)	21(5.6)	10(2.7)	2.1	1.12

Source (Field Survey Data, 2022)

The first measure of employee motivation was guaranteed payments and improvement in salaries in which the study respondents rated the four items. The mean indicates the average rating of employee motivation, when its above 3.0, it is high and implies that employees are highly motivated and below 3.0, it is low mean and implies low employee motivation. From the findings, majority, 100(36.8%) of the respondents indicated that their salaries and allowances were paid on time, which is also indicated by a low mean (M=1.9, STD=.97). Majority, 139(51.1%) of the respondents also disagreed that the salary they received was linked to the work they do, which was affirmed by a low mean (M=2.2, STD). The findings further shows a low rating (M=2.0, STD) where majority of the respondents, 110(40.4%) also strongly disagreed that they receive additional payment when their performance exceeds their targets. However, from the findings, there was a high rating on the statement that the current employment benefits package is fair and equitable (M=3.1, STD=1.28) although with very high variations from the mean response as indicated by the standard deviation and with majority, 91(33.5%) disagreeing.

The second measure of employee motivation was provision of award and promotion. These were also measured by four items. From the findings, majority of the respondents, 105(38.6%) disagreed that there are opportunities for attending seminars, workshops and tours sponsored by county government for good performance, which was also reflected by low mean (M=2.3, STD=1.20). The findings also shows that majority of the respondents, 116(42.6%) disagreed that they were provided with individual awards for better performance, which was also indicated by a low mean (M=2.5, STD=.089). It is clear from the findings that majority of the respondents, 128(47.1%) disagreed that employees who perform well in their role are fairly promoted and rewarded, which is also indicated by a low mean (M=2.4, STD=.97). Finally, there

was a low rating on the county government’s use of reward based performance system made known to employees as indicated by cumulative majority 156(57.4%) , of the respondents either disagreed or strongly disagreed.

The third measure of employee motivation was improved working conditions, which was also indicated using four items. Majority of the respondents, 105(38.6%) disagreed that the county government provided suitable job match to employee to meet employee preference, which was also show by a low mean (M=2.5, STD=1.00). Majority, 130(47.8%) of the respondents disagreed that they were allowed to review their career plan annually to meet short term and long term goals of the county government, which was also reflected by low mean (M=2.1, STD=.99). From the findings, majority, 100(36.8%) of the respondents strongly disagreed that the county government is informative to employee on current changes, trends and future expectations, which is shown by a low mean (M=1.9, STD=.97). Finally, majority, 117(43.0%) of the respondents revealed that the county government value employees personal suggestions on what constitute a good working environment, which is also indicated by a low mean (M2.1, STD=1.12). From these findings, it was be deduced that there is low employee motivation rating in Kisumu county.

➤ *Appraisal Feedback and Employee Motivation*

The study sought to determine the influence of appraisal system feedback on employees’ motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya. Therefore respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which under-listed factors influenced their attitude towards performance appraisal. Each statement was given on scores of 1-5 where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. The findings are presented as shown in Table 3 using frequency counts, percentages, means and standard deviations.

Table 3 Employee Appraisal Feedback

Appraisal Feedback	1	2	3	4	5	M	STD
Supervisors and directors usually seek for employee feedback after appraisal process to capture their thoughts.	114(30.6)	109(29.3)	107(28.8)	18(4.8)	24(6.5)	2.2	1.12
There is a regular evaluation and performance feedback on quarterly basis so that employees may have a chance for improvement.	162(43.5)	94(25.3)	57(15.3)	37(9.9)	22(5.9)	2.0	1.15
Performance appraisal results have impact on my behavior, attitude and morale.	90(24.2)	168(45.2)	74(19.9)	24(6.5)	16(4.3)	2.1	0.94
Feedback process is usually confidential, fair and with objectivity.	160(43)	66(17.7)	90(24.2)	30(8.1)	26(7)	2.1	1.17
I always get the expected results of the performance evaluation and usually agree with the evaluation results.	203(54.6)	78(21)	57(15.3)	13(3.5)	21(5.6)	1.9	1.20
Feedback is sought from employee to determine the degree of technical know-how and job process.	57(15.3)	174(46.8)	118(31.7)	10(2.7)	13(3.5)	2.4	0.95
Your manager communicates with you frequently about your performance.	94(25.3)	143(38.4)	104(28)	23(6.2)	8(2.2)	2.2	1.00
Directors and supervisors usually summon employees who register unsatisfactory performance so as to correct, boost and motivate them to perform.	134(36)	144(38.7)	58(15.6)	27(7.3)	9(2.4)	2.1	1.06

From the findings on employee feedback as indicated in Table 3, majority of the respondents, 85(31.3%) strongly disagreed that supervisors and directors do not usually seek for employee feedback after appraisal process to capture their thoughts, which was also confirmed by a low mean (M=2.2, STD=1.12). The findings also revealed that majority of employees, 124(45.6%) strongly disagreed that there is a regular evaluation and performance feedback on quarterly basis so that employees may have a chance for improvement. This was also confirmed by a low mean (M=2.1, STD=1.15) and a high standard deviation which implies that there was high variation on the response. The findings further shows that feedback process is usually confidential, fair and with objectivity as indicated by a low mean (M=2.1, STD=1.17) and also majority, 123(45.2%) who strongly disagreed. Furthermore, majority of the respondents, 127(46.7%) disagreed that performance appraisal results have impact on their behavior, attitude and morale, which was also shown by a low mean (M=2.1, STD= 0.94) and a low standard deviation which reflects a low variation from the mean. Majority of the respondents, 145(53.3%) strongly disagreed that they always get the

expected results of the performance evaluation and usually agree with the evaluation results (M=1.9, STD=1.20). From the findings, it emerged that feedback is not sought from employees to determine the degree of technical know-how and job process (M=2.4, STD=0.95), which is also indicated by majority of the respondents, 124(45.6%) who disagreed. Majority, 103(37.9%) of the respondents disagreed that their managers communicated with them frequently about their performance, which is indicated by a low mean (M=2.2, STD=1.00). Finally, the findings shows that majority, 104(38.2%) disagreed that directors and supervisors usually summon employees who register unsatisfactory performance so as to correct, boost and motivate them to perform. Further analysis was done in order to test the null hypothesis that “H₀2: Appraisal system feedback does not have a significant influence on employees’ motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya”. This was accomplished using simple linear regression model whereby employee motivation was regressed against performance appraisal criteria. The findings are presented as shown in Table 4. below.

Table 4 Effect of Appraisal System Feedback on Employee Motivation

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.644 ^a	.415	.413	.38203	.415	191.519	1	370	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), AF									
Coefficients ^a									
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.		
		B	Std. Error	Beta					
1	(Constant)	1.091	.204			5.339	.000		
	AF	.692	.050	.644		13.839	.000		

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Motivation

KEY: AF-Appraisal Feedback, Source (Field Survey, 2023)

The findings shows that appraisal criteria accounts for 41.5% variance in employee motivation, R²=.415, F(1, 370)=191.519, p<.05, findings that are significant at p value of 0.05. This means that appraisal feedback accounts for a significant amount of variance in employee motivation, leaving other variance (58.5%) to be accounted for by other variables not in the model. In addition, the findings shows that appraisal feedback has a positive and significant effect on employee motivation (β=.644, p<.05), implying that for a one unit improvement in appraisal feedback, employee motivation improves by a magnitude of 0.644 units according to the scale used. The model unstandardized coefficient as indicated in Table 4.4 reveals that while holding all other variables constant, appraisal feedback uniquely improves employee motivation by 0.313 units (B=0.313, p<.05). This means that the organizations under study have slightly embraced their appraisal feedback, which is having a positive impact on employee motivation. It can thus be concluded that appraisal feedback has a significant influence on employee motivation and therefore we reject the null hypothesis and adopt an alternative hypothesis that appraisal feedback has a significant influence on employee motivation. The aforementioned findings are in line with Oyaro (2017) findings which

showed that provision of feedback influenced teachers’ attitude towards performance appraisal. The findings also concurs with Boadi (2016) findings which concluded that performance appraisal in the civil service is fair, satisfactory and result oriented as well as Prasad (2015) which showed that performance appraisal helps employees to improve their performance by giving feedback about the need for the development. These findings also support previous studies such as Kihama and Wainaina (2019), Kisang and Kirai (2016) and Otieno (2016) in different sectors, which all affirms that appraisal system feedback has a positive influence on employee motivation. These findings also support both the goal setting and expectancy theories which both affirm the role of appraisal system on employees. This leads to the conclusion that system appraisal feedback has a positive and significant influence on employee motivation.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The first objective of the study was to establish the influence of appraisal system criteria on employees’ motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya. Descriptive findings revealed that appraisal system criteria was practiced to a very small extend in the county. Using

multiple and simple linear regression models, the findings revealed that appraisal system criteria however had a positive and significant effect on employee motivation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

From the first objective of the study, it was established that appraisal system criteria has a positive and significant effect on employees' motivation at County Government of Kisumu, Kenya. A good appraisal system takes care of employee's actual performance without any prejudice or witch-hunting and therefore there is proper justice. This is likely to enhance their motivation as they remain positive about it hence knowing that in the event of rewards or any action, there is a good system that is right. Therefore they remain motivated. Following this, the null hypothesis that appraisal system criteria does not have a significant influence on employee motivation was rejected and an alternative hypothesis which states that appraisal criteria has a significant influence on employee motivation adopted. It can thus be concluded that appraisal system criteria has a positive and significant influence on employee motivation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the first objective of the study, it is recommended that the county government comes up with effective, efficient and more advanced system appraisal criteria that will satisfy employees to maintain a positive attitude in their leadership and hence remain motivated.

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